

REAL-TIME MONITORING OF GROUNDWATER TREATMENT IN AN AREA WITH HYDROCARBON POLLUTION

Nikolay G. Makisomovch^{1,2}, Vadim T. Khmurchik^{1,2}, Artem D. Demenev^{1,2}, Olga A. Berezina^{1,2}, Olga Yu. Meshcheriakova^{1,2}

¹LLC «MIP «Geoinnovation plus», Perm, Russian Federation, E-mail: nmax54@gmail.com

² Perm State University, Perm, Russian Federation

ABSTRACT: *Treatment of groundwater from dissolved oil and oil products is one of the priority tasks when carrying out a set of environmental protection measures. A promising action to eliminate such pollution is biological destruction of it. The authors have developed a special device that makes it possible to create the most acceptable conditions for the life of oil-oxidizing microorganisms through a dosed supply of oxygen, and organized operational monitoring of hydrochemical parameters of polluted groundwaters. Continuous monitoring of the functioning of the groundwater treatment system is one of the most important tools for the efficiency of the same environmental protection measures. Similar monitoring, using traditional methods with sampling and measurements, entails significant financial costs, so the most appropriate is to perform monitoring of groundwater treatment using specialized sensors, telemetry devices, and online services for storing, processing and visualizing data.*

Key words: *groundwater treatment, dissolved petroleum products, remote monitoring, environmental technologies*

The processes of oil and gas recovery, transportation, and processing could influence on environmental components (Davydova & Tagasov 2004). Accident cases could be accompanied by the formation of sources of environment pollution with oil and oil products at certain circumstances (Solntseva 1998; Faschuk *et al.* 2003). The rate of migration of oil pollution depends on the environment conditions and the intensity of pollutants entering the environment. Over time, oil or oil products enter groundwater and begin readily migrate with water flow being in dissolved form.

At present, a numerous methods and technologies are used to clean water bodies from oil pollution, but the problem of the spreading of dissolved oil products in groundwater remains often unresolved.

A promising action to eliminate groundwater pollution by dissolved oil products is biological destruction of these products.

It is believed that all substances of biological origin, oil and oil products included, can be oxidized, and in nature there will always be microorganisms capable of oxidizing and destroying them completely or partially. Biological methods of hydrocarbons destruction are used in cases when hydrocarbon quantity is too small to apply mechanical cleaning methods, but too large to use contaminated land and water for economic purposes. Our team carries out research on the cleaning of underground aquifers with biological methods using both bio-stimulation of the community of natural hydrocarbon-oxidizing microorganisms (Demenev *et al.* 2022) and bio-augmentation of autochthonous hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria with their active biomass (Maksimovich & Khmurchik 2006, 2015; Maksimovich *et al.* 2009). Bio-augmentation was carried out by introducing the active biomass of microorganisms into the well directly, or using a special device (Maksimovich *et al.* 2009a).

A special device (the well multi-channel injector) was designed, which allows to develop in wells conditions most acceptable for the vital activity of oil-oxidizing microorganisms due to the dosed supply of oxygen.

One of the most important tools for the developed technological complex performance controlling is the ongoing monitoring of the groundwater treatment system functioning. It is known that to start a more effective destruction of hydrocarbon pollutants, it is necessary to achieve concentrations of water-dissolved oxygen 5-10 mg/dm³ (Yaniga *et al.* 1985). Thus, the concentration of oxygen dissolved in groundwater is a parameter that allows to monitor the efficiency of the well multi-channel injector operation in continuous mode.

Depending on the monitoring results, a decision may be adopted to adjust the treatment of the aquifer, to replace the oxygen supply source, or to repair equipment. In this regard, it is a fundamental requirement to ensure operational monitoring of controlled parameters in real time mode. The same monitoring, using traditional methods with sampling and measurements, entails significant financial costs, therefore, the most appropriate is to monitor controlled parameters using specialized sensors, telemetry devices and online services for data storage, processing and visualization. Further, operator has the opportunity to interact with the monitoring system via the web interface (Fig. 1). He will have access to operational and archived measurement data obtained from any used sensor.

Figure 1. Web interface of the service for collecting data from an autonomous sensor (the graph shows the change in the content of dissolved oxygen after the start of its dosed supply into groundwater)

Based on the field-testing results of the well multi-channel injector using, it can be concluded that the designed technical device had confirmed their efficiency. The oxygen saturation of groundwater was observed throughout the entire experimental work, hydrochemical parameters were stably transmitted to the server wirelessly, and the data were analyzed and processed subsequently.

In the future, at other contaminated objects, it is recommended to perform similar monitoring with a lower data transmission frequency (for example, 2 data transmissions a day), depending on the geological, lithological, hydrogeological and geomorphological conditions of the territory.

References:

- Davydova S.L., Tagasov V.I. 2004: *Oil and oil products in the environment*. M.: Publishing House of RUDN, 163 p.
- Demenev A., Maksimovich N., Khmurchik V., Rogovskiy G., Rogovskiy A., Baryshnikov A. 2022: *Field test of in situ groundwater applying oxygen diffusion and bioaugmentation methods in an area with sustained total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) contaminant flow*, Water, Vol. 14, article 192.
- Maksimovich N.G., Khmurchik V.T. 2006: *Consortium of strains of hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria Pseudomonas aeruginosa nd kz-1 and Pseudomonas fluorescens nd kz-2 as a destructor of oil products and a method for cleaning of oil-contaminated groundwater*. Patent of the Russian Federation No. 2312719; application. 02/15/2006; publ. 12/20/2007, Bul. No. 35.
- Faschuk D.Ya., Ovsienko S.N., Leonov A.V. and others. 2003: *Geoecological consequences of accidental oil spills*, Izvestiya RAS. Geography, No. 5, pp. 135-150.
- Maksimovich N.G., Khmurchik V.T. 2015: *Remediation of oil-polluted groundwater aquifers at karst region*, Engineering geology for society and territory, Vol. 3 "River basins, reservoir sedimentation and water resources" (Lollino G. et al., Eds.), Springer, pp. 417-419.

- Maksimovich N.G., Khmurchik V.T., Meshcheriakova O.Yu. 2009:*Experience of groundwater purification from oil pollution by biological methods*, Industrial safety and Ecology, № 4 (37),pp. 34-36.
- Maksimovich N.G., Khmurchik V.T., Meshcheriakova O.Yu. 2009a: *The experience of groundwater cleaning from oil pollution by biological methods*, Industrial safety and ecology, № 4 (37),pp. 34-36.
- Solntseva N.P. 1998:*Oil recovery and geochemistry of natural landscapes*. M.: Publishing House of Moscow State University, 376 p.
- Yaniga, P.M., Matson, C., Demko, D.J. 1985: *Restoration of water quality in a multi-aquifer system via in situ biodegradation of the organic contaminants*, Proceedings of the Fifth National Symposium and Exposition on Aquifer Restoration and Ground Water Monitoring, Worthington, OH, USA, 21-24 May 1985; National Water Well Association: Worthington, OH, USA, 510 p.

